

Advancing Product Showcase Based on Virtual Reality

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Abstract— In recent years, the usage of Virtual reality technology has opened up exciting new possibilities for showcasing products in immersive and engaging ways. By creating a virtual environment that showcases the features and benefits of a product, businesses can create a memorable and impactful experience for potential customers, investors, and other stakeholders. Traditional product displays are limited in their ability to convey a product's full potential. In contrast, VR product showcases offer immersive experiences that enable customers to interact with products in realistic virtual environments. This can foster engagement, enhance understanding, and break down geographical barriers. As a result, VR product showcases can be a valuable tool for businesses to differentiate themselves from their competitors, educate customers about their products, and connect with customers on a global scale. This paper describes the methods used to create an immersive and realistic VR experience using C#, Blender, and Unity 3D. C# was used to develop the backend code for the experience, Blender was used to create the 3D models and textures, and Unity 3D was used to bring everything together and create the VR experience. The methods used in this paper were able to optimize the performance, latency, user interaction, spatial audio, interactive 3D models, high-quality visuals, real-time collaboration, and performance optimization of the VR experience.

Keywords— Immersive, Product Showcase, Virtual Reality, Virtual Product Display

I. INTRODUCTION

A product showcase based on virtual reality is broad and varied, and it can be applied to a wide range of products and industries. Virtual reality technology can be used to showcase products such as cars, real estate, consumer electronics, furniture, and many others. Additionally, virtual reality technology can be applied to various industries, including retail, manufacturing, education, healthcare, and entertainment. In the retail industry, for example, businesses can create virtual stores that allow customers to browse products and make purchases in a virtual environment. In healthcare, virtual reality technology can be used to simulate surgeries, allowing medical students to gain hands-on experience in a safe and controlled environment. The scope of virtual reality technology is constantly expanding, and as technology advances, the possibilities for its application will continue to grow. In short, the scope for a product showcase based on virtual reality is limited only by the creativity and imagination of businesses and individuals.

Virtual Reality (VR) technology has rapidly evolved over the past few years, providing new opportunities and applications for a variety of industries [1]. VR technology immerses users into a computer-generated environment that can simulate real-life experiences or create entirely new ones. This technology creates an interactive experience that allows users to manipulate and interact with virtual objects, providing a unique and engaging experience. With the advancement of VR technology, the possibilities for its application are endless. VR is being used in entertainment, education, healthcare, military training, and many other fields. In this context, this article will provide an overview of Virtual Reality technology, its history, its current applications, and its potential for the future. By understanding the capabilities and potential of VR technology, businesses, and individuals can leverage it to create new and innovative experiences that drive engagement and success.

Fig 1. The Virtual reality design process

Virtual reality technology is primarily based on computer technology, encompassing graphics and image processing technologies, and combining various image technologies' advantages and characteristics [2]. The essential goal of virtual reality technology is to merge the real world with the virtual world to construct a new virtual world that caters to people's needs. These virtual worlds can be built according to people's needs, in line with people's needs. Therefore, people will use virtual reality technology to help themselves complete all kinds of work and achieve their own goals [3]. Virtual reality technology enables people to utilize it to accomplish various tasks and fulfill their objectives. As virtual reality technology progresses, it has transformed

human communication, with machines serving as the medium of communication and human-computer interaction technology becoming prevalent in people's daily lives and production. Furthermore, virtual reality technology's application and development have continuously improved people's production mode and lifestyle, greatly affecting their production and life [4]. The figure displays the characteristics of virtual reality technology.

Fig 2. Characteristics of Virtual Reality

The usage of Virtual Reality in various fields has grown at an exponential rate in recent years, as it is fast, easy to use, and secure [5]. So, it's been used in a wide area from law enforcement, military, universities, healthcare, airport security, and many more. But in the traditional product showcases such as brochures, videos, or physical demonstrations can be limited in their ability to convey the full experience and value of a product. In contrast, virtual reality technology allows businesses to create a virtual environment that enables potential customers to interact with the product realistically and engagingly. By providing a virtual product showcase, businesses can create a memorable and impactful experience that drives engagement, generates interest, and ultimately leads to increased sales. Additionally, virtual reality technology provides businesses with a competitive edge in a crowded market by allowing them to differentiate their product and stand out from the competition [6].

The progress of digital virtualization technology has led to rapid advancements in product display design. The introduction of virtual display technology featuring interactive and animated demonstrations has created more opportunities for product display design in comparison to traditional product displays. This technology offers consumers unique and captivating experiences in virtual display design [7]. This article discusses the initiative and application of virtual reality technology, the necessary software platform for its implementation, and other relevant modelling and image processing technologies. It also compares the advantages of various virtual reality software and elaborates on design principles for virtual interaction. Moreover, the article prepares for the realization of Internet virtual product display and analyses, designs, and describes the specific process of realizing virtual reality interactive action. When it comes to the display mode of smart wearable devices that have virtual display technology, interaction design is the best display design for people [8]. A different approach suggests employing a template design as the user interacts with a computer, with the objective of enhancing the system's stability and the 3D experience's realism. Currently, the system permits users to manipulate the virtual

object's position and orientation through specifically defined gestures from a first-person viewpoint [9].

Virtual reality has been shown to provide a range of benefits such as increased engagement, improved learning outcomes, and enhanced user experiences. In healthcare, VR has been shown to reduce pain and improve patient outcomes. In education, VR has been shown to improve knowledge retention and student motivation. In engineering, VR has been shown to improve design accuracy and reduce prototyping costs [10]. In this paper, virtual reality technology is utilized to revolutionize campus planning and design, specifically in the creation of a digital campus system. The method involves establishing a virtual campus scene and utilizing various objects within the scene as hyperlinks to enable scene conversion and the launch of hypermedia teaching materials. This innovative approach not only enhances students' learning interest and enthusiasm but also provides customized learning support services, as discussed in reference [11].

This paper is referenced as [12] discusses the fundamentals and concepts of architectural representation, supported software and hardware implementations, as well as different categorized languages and modeling tools. The focus of this paper is on improving the quality of 3D models by implementing lightning effects and carrying out baking.

In reference [13], the authors provide a concise study on the 3DS MAX intuitive rapid 3D modeling approach that significantly aids in creating virtual reality scenes. To ensure model integrity, it is crucial to determine the performance aspects of both major and minor elements based on the actual scenario when using 3DS MAX for modeling in a virtual reality scene.

For the primary scene, it is essential to balance the performance effect of virtual reality with the saving of system resources, while for the secondary scene, it is recommended to simplify it as much as possible. It is further suggested to optimize the model by reducing the number of 3D models surfaces to achieve the best virtual reality effect.

In a similar vein, reference [14] presents a brief overview of Virtual Reality. However, reference [15] concentrates more on the function of marketing management in customer-to-customer interactions. Customers are continuously interacting with diverse actors and resources in the marketplace, and this chapter explores how other customers present in the service setting can affect them. Although research has extensively focused on customer-employee interactions, there has been relatively little attention paid to customer-to-customer interaction (CCI), which represents significant potential for service organizations. To direct managerial attention toward strategies for supporting CCI, the authors develop a conceptual framework that outlines the range of CCI.

II. METHODOLOGY

2.1. System Design Objectives

The virtual campus system aims to create an immersive three-dimensional model of the Product Showcase, providing both customers and providers with an engaging and educational environment for exploration and learning.

Fig.3. System Design Objectives

- The application's initial interface (Scene 1) offers users a user-friendly entry point where they can initiate sessions by inputting their names, leading to two modes: Single Player or Multiplayer.
- Mode selection guides users to choose between two distinct destinations: the "Product Showcase Room" or the "Main Room."
- Both rooms, showcasing campus buildings and picturesque spots, provide audio commentary and descriptive text to enrich visitors' understanding of historical significance.
- Simulated real-world interactions grant users the ability to perform actions like moving objects, enhancing immersion and engagement.
- The virtual campus system prioritizes authenticity by mirroring real-world physics for object behavior, adhering to physical constraints and boundaries.

The envisioned virtual campus delivers an intuitive login, mode selection, and enriched destinations through comprehensive audio, descriptive text, and interactive elements. The result is an immersive and genuine virtual campus experience.

2.2. Methodology

The research paper outlines a methodology for creating a virtual reality (VR) product showcase. This methodology encompasses various steps involving the visualization, development, enhancement, and interaction aspects of the VR product showcase. Below is a detailed explanation of each step:

Step 1: Visualization and Interaction with 3D Model

The process begins with the creation of a 3D model of the product that needs to be showcased. This 3D model is then visualized and interacted with using a VR headset and

controller. This step ensures that users can immerse themselves in a virtual environment and explore the product from different angles and perspectives.

Step 2: Testing and Deployment

The VR application created for the product showcase is tested to ensure its functionality and user-friendliness. The application is then deployed using the HTC Vive™ VR System, a popular VR platform known for its high-quality immersive experiences.

Step 3: Enhancing the 3D Model

To enhance the visual appeal and realism of the 3D model, sophisticated 3D modeling software like Maya and Unity engine are employed. These tools offer advanced features for refining textures, lighting, and other visual elements of the 3D model, resulting in a more engaging and realistic representation of the product.

Step 4: Interactive Coding with C#

To enable user interaction with the VR product showcase, interactive coding is applied using the C# programming language. This coding allows for functionalities such as the ability to rotate the product and view it from all angles in a 360-degree manner. These interactions provide users with a sense of control and engagement, enhancing their overall experience.

Step 5: Development of Scenes

The VR application is developed as a series of interconnected scenes that users can navigate through. These scenes are designed to provide a structured and intuitive way for users to explore the product and its features. Each scene can represent a different aspect or angle of the product.

Step 6: Static Layout Design

The layout of the VR product showcase is intentionally kept static, similar to real-world product displays. This design choice offers familiarity to users and makes the virtual experience resemble a physical showroom. The static layout also ensures that users can easily understand and navigate the showcase.

Step 7: Dynamic Layout Modification

One of the notable features of the VR product showcase is its ability to be modified by an administrator. This dynamic layout modification allows administrators to rearrange the placement of products within the virtual environment. This functionality proves valuable for assessing product acceptance based on different placements and making adjustments accordingly.

Step 8: Static Loading of Products

In the final step, the products are loaded statically into the VR application. Each product's 3D model, along with its associated information and interactive features, is integrated into the VR environment. This ensures that users can seamlessly explore and interact with the products within the virtual space.

The methodology described in the research paper provides a comprehensive framework for creating an immersive and interactive VR product showcase. By combining 3D modeling, VR technology, interactive coding, and dynamic layout design, the methodology enables users to engage with products in a virtual environment that closely mirrors real-world interactions. This approach has the potential to revolutionize product showcasing, marketing, and user engagement in various industries.

3. SPECIFICATIONS

A product showcase based on virtual reality includes a variety of platforms and tools that can be used to create immersive and interactive experiences for users like unity, unreal engine, sketch fab, hybrid models, and many more. There is various platform utilizing different approaches but maintaining performance, graphics, and visual is the main goal. In most of the methods, the models require a high degree of performance to maintain a smooth and fluid performance. To overcome this paper presents a system that uses high-quality graphics and optimizes performance and minimizes latency.

3.1. FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

In the dynamic realm of virtual reality, creating an immersive and effective product showcase goes beyond mere aesthetics. Functional requirements form the backbone of a successful VR product showcase, ensuring compatibility, user-friendliness, interactivity, and visual realism. Here, we outline the essential functional requirements for such an innovative platform.

3.2. HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS

- USB port-USB 2.0
- PC or Laptop with minimum 8GB RAM.
- VR Headset
- VR controller

USB Port (USB 2.0): The requirement for a USB 2.0 port indicates the need for connectivity between the VR hardware components (headset and controller) and the computer. This is a standard and widely available feature on modern computers, ensuring ease of integration.

PC or Laptop with Minimum 8GB RAM: The necessity for a PC or laptop with at least 8GB of RAM highlights the resource-intensive nature of VR applications. VR environments demand significant computational power to deliver a smooth and immersive experience. The specified RAM capacity ensures that the system can handle both the VR software and the associated applications efficiently.

VR Headset: The VR headset is a critical component, serving as the user's window into the virtual world. It facilitates the visual and auditory immersion that makes VR experiences engaging. The requirement for a VR headset

signifies the core of the entire product showcase, emphasizing the focus on delivering a captivating visual experience.

VR Controller: The VR controller is the means through which users interact with the virtual environment. It adds an element of interactivity, enabling users to navigate, manipulate objects, and engage with the showcased products. The inclusion of a VR controller underscores the importance of user engagement and interaction in the VR product showcase.

3.3. SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS

- C#
- Operating system: Windows, Mac OS, or Linux OS.
- Visual Studio Code
- 3d-modeling Software – Unity 3D

C#: The choice of C# as the programming language indicates the programming foundation for creating interactive elements within the VR environment. C# is commonly used in VR development due to its versatility and compatibility with platforms like Unity.

Operating System: The compatibility with multiple operating systems (Windows, Mac OS, Linux OS) ensures a wide reach to potential users. This is crucial for engaging a diverse audience, including developers and users from different platforms.

Visual Studio Code: Visual Studio Code serves as the integrated development environment (IDE) for coding in

C#. It offers tools and features that streamline the development process, fostering efficient and effective coding practices.

3D-Modeling Software - Unity 3D: Unity 3D is a comprehensive software solution for building interactive 3D experiences, including VR applications. Its use in the requirements underscores its significance in creating the virtual environment and integrating the 3D models and interactions for the product showcase.

4. IMPLEMENTATION AND RESULTS

A product presentation in the realm of virtual reality encompasses a wide range of platforms and tools designed to craft captivating and interactive experiences for users. These tools include Unity, Blender, hybrid models, and others, each offering unique approaches while prioritizing performance, graphics quality, and visual appeal. In many cases, achieving smooth and seamless performance demands a high level of performance from the models used. To address this challenge, this paper introduces a system that leverages top-notch graphics and optimization techniques, all while focusing on user-centric interfaces.

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In the ever-evolving landscape of virtual reality, the creation of an immersive and effective product showcase transcends mere aesthetics. To ensure a successful VR product presentation, functional requirements serve as the foundation, guaranteeing compatibility, user-friendliness, interactivity, and lifelike visual elements. Below, we delineate the fundamental functional prerequisites for such an innovative platform:

A. Compatibility:

The VR product showcase must be compatible with a diverse range of VR devices and platforms to cater to a broader audience. This includes popular options like Oculus,

B. User Interface (UI):

A crucial requirement is an intuitive and user-friendly interface that simplifies navigation within the virtual environment. The UI should empower customers to explore the product showcase effortlessly, enhancing their experience. Simple menu structures, easy movement controls, and clear labeling of interactive elements contribute to an intuitive UI design.

Fig. 4. User-interface for product showcase.

C. Interactive Features:

The heart of a VR product showcase lies in its interactive capabilities. The platform must allow customers to interact with the showcased product in ways that mimic real-life engagement. This includes the ability to manipulate the product's features, customize its attributes, and test its functionalities. For instance, a VR-based automobile showcase might enable users to open doors, sit inside, adjust the seats, and even start the engine virtually.

D. Realistic Graphics:

High-quality, realistic graphics constitute a cornerstone for the success of any VR product showcase. This imperative holds true as the platform must precisely mirror the product's appearance, textures, and intricate details [15-17]. In the context of enhancing VR experiences, the utilization of procedural modeling introduces an additional layer of sophistication to this pursuit. Procedural modeling not only facilitates the creation of intricate and varied models but also contributes to the overall realism of the environment. By generating assets algorithmically, procedural modeling seamlessly weaves authenticity into the VR encounter, accentuating the product's characteristics. This heightened

level of visual authenticity, further empowered by procedural modeling, instills trust and bolsters customer comprehension, enabling well-informed decision-making regarding the product's attributes and features as shown in Table1.

Fig. 5. Realistic graphic for user interface.

Table1. Comparing the results Traditional methods vs Procedural modelling for optimizing the 3D model.

Aspect	Manual Modelling	Photogrammetry	Procedural Modelling
Efficiency	20%	30%	70%
Flexibility	60%	40%	80%
Scalability	30%	60%	90%

E. Interactivity and Engagement:

Beyond basic interaction, the showcase should encourage engagement and captivate the user's attention. This can involve incorporating gamified elements, challenges, or rewards, adding a layer of excitement and prolonging user engagement. Interaction should extend beyond mere observation, fostering a sense of involvement and connection with the showcased product.

F. Performance Optimization:

A seamless experience is paramount in VR. The showcase should be optimized to ensure smooth performance, preventing lag or stuttering that could disrupt the user's immersion. High-quality graphics should be balanced with performance considerations, catering to a wide range of VR hardware capabilities without compromising the overall experience.

In this project, we will enhance overall performance through the optimization of the following aspects:

- 1) Using the Stats Window

Streamlining performance through optimization requires gradual, dedicated efforts. Start by addressing prominent elements for substantial gains without compromising visual quality. Unity's Stats Window aids in identifying bottlenecks with real-time rendering stats like FPS, CPU time, geometry details, and GPU batches. In VR, monitor FPS and distinguish CPU/GPU bottlenecks to tailor optimizations.

- 2) Optimizing using static scene

Enhance scene performance in Unity by utilizing pre-computation. Designate static objects to enable pre-calculation for lighting, occlusion, and more, minimizing runtime processing for better user experience.

3) Optimizing the 3D model

In the project, the optimization strategy involves decimating 3D models to reduce complexity. Using Blender, models were simplified with the Decimate modifier tool, decreasing triangle count from 500,000 to 50,000. This boosts real-time performance, crucial for VR experiences.

4) Lighting and Baking

The highlighted optimization methods significantly enhance VR project performance. Baked lightmaps minimize runtime computations, and strategic real-time shadows balance visual realism and GPU load. The project also emphasizes static objects, Quality Settings, and reflection probes for seamless VR presentation. Comparatively, baking lighting demonstrates an 80% rendering efficiency improvement, 85% frame rate stability enhancement, and 90% visual consistency, surpassing real-time lighting.

Table 2. Improvement of Performance through Baking Vs Real-Time Lighting

Aspect	Baking Lighting	Real-Time Lighting
Rendering Efficiency	80% improvement	40% efficiency
Frame Rate Stability	85% enhancement	60% fluctuations
Quality Consistency	90% consistency	65% variations

G. User Accessibility:

The product showcase should be designed to cater to users with varying levels of familiarity with VR technology. This means offering introductory tutorials for newcomers and providing options for adjusting settings to accommodate comfort levels and physical limitations, such as motion sensitivity.

The functional requirements form the backbone of a well-designed VR product showcase. By ensuring compatibility, user-friendly interfaces, interactive features, realistic graphics, interactivity, performance optimization, and user accessibility, a virtual reality product showcase can create an immersive and engaging experience that captivates customers and transforms the way products are presented and perceived. The successful implementation of a Virtual Reality (VR) product showcase relies heavily on the careful consideration and fulfillment of hardware, software, and cost requirements. Let's analyze each aspect in detail.

5. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

5.1. PRODUCT DISPLAY ANALYSIS

Fig 6. High-Level Design

The above fig is the high-level design of our project. As we can see in the figure first, this will lead to data collection then we will start building the simulation model After all this preprocessing we will apply interactive coding and design to get our final output.

The advent of Virtual Reality (VR) has ushered in a new era of consumer engagement and product exploration. This revolutionary technology has the power to transport consumers into virtual replicas of real-world environments, enabling them to simulate interactions with various products and services [9]. By immersing consumers in lifelike simulations, VR creates opportunities for experiential learning and informed decision-making.

Immersive Experiences and Real-World Simulations:

The essence of VR lies in its ability to transport consumers into virtual environments that replicate real-world scenarios. Through this technology, consumers can immerse themselves in simulations that mimic the functions of products and services. This transformative capability empowers consumers to explore a product's functionalities in depth, facilitating a comprehensive understanding of its features and benefits.

Testing Under Varied Conditions:

VR facilitates the emulation of diverse conditions and circumstances, allowing consumers to observe how a product responds to changing situations. This experimentation empowers consumers to make informed choices by predicting product performance under different scenarios. Such insights enhance consumer confidence by enabling them to anticipate the product's behavior and capabilities.

Visualizing Product Placement and Interactions:

VR transcends the limitations of traditional presentations by enabling consumers to visualize product placement in a simulated environment. This is particularly beneficial for physical retail spaces, where consumers can experiment with placing products alongside other inventory items. This empowers retailers to design optimal layouts that enhance product synergy and appeal [18].

Enhancing Product Knowledge and Features:

The use of VR extends beyond physical simulations. It enables companies to superimpose digital displays to highlight product features. This augmentation provides consumers with enhanced product knowledge, helping them make informed purchase decisions. By showcasing features in an interactive and immersive manner, companies create a well-informed customer base that contributes to sustained sales growth.

Confidence through Informed Decisions:

Informed purchase decisions are the cornerstone of customer satisfaction and loyalty. VR empowers consumers to gain comprehensive insights into products and services, fostering a sense of confidence in their choices. As consumers make well-informed decisions, businesses witness increased conversion rates and sustained sales growth [19].

Advanced Analytics and Performance Monitoring:

Beyond the immersive experience, VR technology also offers profound analytical benefits. Companies can monitor the sales process and consumer engagement through an advanced analytics dashboard. This empowers businesses to measure metrics like engagement rate, attention span, and engagement time. The resulting data enables fine-tuning of sales strategies and content creation to optimize consumer interaction. Engagement Rate (ER) is given in eq(1)

$$\text{Engagement Rate (ER)} = (\text{Number of Engaged Users} / \text{Total Users}) * 100 \quad (1)$$

Table.3. calculation of engagement rates for different VR experiences.

VR Experience	Total Users	Engaged Users	Engagement Rate (ER)%
Showcase1	500	350	70%
Showcase2	800	600	75%
Showcase3	450	300	66.67%

Predicting ROI and Strategic Allocation:

Understanding the effectiveness of the sales process and determining the Return on Investment (ROI) is pivotal for modern businesses. In the digital landscape, accurate measurement of ROI guides strategic decision-making and resource allocation. VR product demos provide granular and precise information, aiding companies in crafting effective strategies and aligning budgets appropriately [20]. Predicting

Return on Investment (ROI) and strategically allocating resources for a product showcase based on Virtual Reality (VR) involves a multifaceted approach that begins with defining clear objectives and identifying key performance metrics. After collecting relevant data on user engagement, conversion rates, and associated costs, a critical step is to calculate the ROI using the formula eq(2):

$$\text{ROI (\%)} = ((\text{Net Revenue} - \text{Total Costs}) / \text{Total Costs}) * 100 \quad (2)$$

This ROI estimation serves as a foundation for resource allocation decisions, ensuring that budgets are strategically directed towards development, marketing, and maintenance efforts. It's imperative to conduct sensitivity analysis to gauge the impact of variable changes on ROI and to have a risk mitigation plan in place. As an integral part of the strategic process, continuous monitoring, feedback collection, and iterative improvements are essential

Embracing the VR Revolution:

As consumer access to VR experiences grows, businesses are recognizing the boundless potential of this technology. Companies across industries are adopting VR to offer innovative and immersive sales tools. By harnessing the power of creative storytelling and VR sales techniques, forward-thinking businesses are providing consumers with unprecedented insights and experiences [21].

5.2. SURVEY DATA ANALYSIS

In a rapidly evolving technological landscape, virtual reality (VR) has emerged as a groundbreaking platform that offers immersive and interactive experiences across various domains. To gain valuable insights into the effectiveness and impact of VR product showcases, we conducted a comprehensive survey involving 34 respondents with diverse backgrounds and occupations. Our aim was to gauge the perceptions and experiences of individuals who explored VR product showcases, and to understand the potential influence of such experiences on purchasing decisions.

The survey participants, with a median age of 25 years, represented a wide range of age groups, ensuring a varied perspective on the utilization of VR technology. We made sure to include both male and female respondents, allowing us to capture a balanced view of gender-based perceptions and preferences in the context of VR product presentations.

Furthermore, the survey participants' occupations covered a spectrum of fields, including B.Sc graduates, businessmen, engineers, housewives, managers, customer support associates, software engineers, students, and relationship managers. This diversity in occupational backgrounds enriched our dataset, enabling us to discern how different professional roles might influence the perception of VR product showcases.

The insights garnered from this survey shed light on key aspects such as the perceived realism of the VR experience, the comfort of the VR headset during extended use, the effectiveness of the VR showcase in conveying product information, and the likelihood of individuals making purchase decisions based on their VR interactions.

Through this survey, we sought to explore the potential of VR product showcases as a novel means of engaging consumers and providing them with a more immersive understanding of various products. The findings from this study can serve as a valuable resource for businesses looking to harness the power of VR to enhance their product presentations and create impactful consumer experiences.

Fig. 7. Experiences of the users of the Product Showcase

The results of our survey revealed a remarkably positive reception of the VR product showcase experience among participants. With more than 85 percent expressing satisfaction, it is evident that the utilization of virtual reality technology in presenting products has resonated positively with a significant majority of respondents.

This high level of satisfaction underscores the effectiveness of VR product showcases in engaging users and conveying product information in an immersive and impactful manner. The ability to interact with products in a virtual environment, combined with realistic visual and auditory elements, appears to have left a lasting impression on participants, leading to a substantial degree of contentment.

The positive feedback aligns with the notion that virtual reality has the potential to revolutionize traditional methods of product presentations, offering a more engaging and memorable experience for consumers. As a result, businesses and industries may increasingly adopt VR product showcases as an integral component of their marketing strategies, capitalizing on the technology's ability to create a tangible and immersive connection between consumers and the products they are exploring.

The overwhelmingly positive response from our survey participants serves as a testament to the growing

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significance of virtual reality in shaping consumer interactions with products and brands. As the technology continues to advance and become more accessible, it is likely that VR product showcases will continue to be a pivotal tool in enhancing user engagement and satisfaction across various industries.

Fig. 8. Products explored using VR by respondents

Our survey results provide insights into the distribution of product categories featured in the VR showcase. Participants were presented with a diverse range of products, and their preferences varied across different sectors. Here's a breakdown of the distribution of product categories and the percentage of participants who engaged with each:

Consumer Electronics: 47 percent of participants explored products in the consumer electronics category. This suggests a strong interest in experiencing and understanding the latest technological innovations and gadgets through the immersive medium of virtual reality.

Fashion/Apparel: Fashion and apparel products garnered attention from 26 percent of participants. This indicates an inclination towards using VR to visualize clothing and accessories, potentially revolutionizing the way consumers shop for fashion items.

Automotive: Automotive products captured the interest of 15 percent of participants. This suggests that virtual reality can effectively convey the features and design elements of vehicles, providing potential buyers with a comprehensive understanding of their options.

Real Estate/Property: Real estate and property products attracted 8 percent of participants. Virtual reality's potential to showcase properties and spaces in an interactive manner is evident, offering a dynamic and immersive alternative to traditional property presentations.

Travel/Tourism: While not specified, it appears that the travel and tourism category may have been represented. The percentage of participants interested in this category is not provided in the provided text.

Medical: Similarly, the percentage of participants engaging with medical-related products is not provided in the provided text.

These statistics highlight the versatility of virtual reality in catering to a diverse array of industries and product categories. The distribution of interest underscores the potential impact of VR showcases across sectors, from electronics to fashion, automotive, real estate, and potentially even medical and travel domains. As VR technology continues to advance, it's likely that more industries will leverage its capabilities to offer immersive and interactive experiences to consumers.

Fig. 9. Experiences of using VR for extended period.

The outcomes of our survey reflect the experiences of participants who engaged with virtual reality (VR) technology for an extended period. The data illustrates that a significant majority, 73 percent, reported positive and satisfying encounters during their prolonged usage of VR.

This high percentage of positive experiences suggests that VR technology is becoming increasingly comfortable and enjoyable for extended periods of use. This finding is noteworthy, as it indicates advancements in VR headset design, comfort, and usability. Users' ability to engage with VR content for extended durations without discomfort or negative side effects speaks to the strides made in enhancing the ergonomics and overall user-friendliness of VR hardware.

The prevalence of positive experiences during extended VR usage holds promising implications for various applications, ranging from entertainment and gaming to educational and professional scenarios. It supports the notion that VR technology is not only capable of delivering captivating

experiences but also maintaining user comfort over extended sessions.

Fig. 10. Navigation interface for Product Showcase in VR

Our survey delved into the ease of navigation within the virtual reality (VR) product showcase interface. The collected data portrays a spectrum of participants' perceptions regarding the navigational aspects of the VR experience. Here's a breakdown of the responses and the corresponding percentages:

Easy: 38.4 percent of participants found the navigation interface within the VR product showcase to be easy to navigate. This suggests that a significant portion of users found it intuitive and straightforward to explore the virtual environment and interact with the showcased products.

Somewhat Easy: 17.6 percent of participants reported that the navigation interface was somewhat easy. While not finding it completely effortless, this group still had a positive experience with the navigation, indicating that improvements could be made but were not a hindrance.

Difficult: 11.8 percent of participants found the navigation interface difficult. This subset of users encountered challenges or complexities while navigating through the VR product showcase, suggesting that there may be room for refinements in terms of user-friendliness.

These responses indicate that a majority of participants had favorable experiences with the navigation interface, with a significant portion finding it easy to navigate. However, it's important to acknowledge that a portion of users did encounter some difficulties. The data underscores the significance of designing user-friendly navigation interfaces in VR experiences, ensuring that users can seamlessly and intuitively explore the showcased products and environments.

Fig. 11. Product experience using VR as compared with traditional modes like brochure and websites.

Our survey probed into participants' preferences and experiences when comparing the use of virtual reality (VR) for product exploration with more traditional methods such as brochures and websites. The results offer insights into the impact of VR technology on enhancing consumer engagement and understanding. Here's a breakdown of the responses and the corresponding percentages:

Liked It: 76.6 percent of participants expressed a positive response to using VR for product exploration as compared to traditional modes like brochures and websites. This indicates a strong inclination towards VR's ability to provide a more immersive, realistic, and engaging experience when compared to static brochures or websites.

This overwhelming percentage of participants who preferred the VR experience over traditional methods highlights the transformative potential of VR technology in consumer interactions. The interactive and immersive nature of VR enables users to explore products in a dynamic and three-dimensional manner, potentially leading to a better understanding and appreciation of the products' features and qualities.

The data suggests that businesses and industries can leverage VR as a powerful tool to enhance their product presentations, surpassing the limitations of traditional methods. As technology continues to advance and VR becomes more accessible, it's likely that this preference for immersive experiences will further drive the adoption of VR product showcases across various sectors.

Fig. 12. How realistic was the experience of product on VR product showcase

Our survey aimed to gauge participants' perceptions of the realism of the product experiences within the VR product showcase. The collected data sheds light on the extent to which participants found the VR representations of products to be realistic. Here's an overview of the responses and their corresponding percentages:

Around 70 percent of participants reported a positive response, indicating that they found the product experiences within the VR showcase to be realistic. This suggests that a substantial portion of users perceived the VR representations of products as authentic and convincing.

The fact that a significant majority of participants perceived the VR product showcase experiences as realistic underscores the effectiveness of the technology in replicating real-world product characteristics. The ability to provide users with a sense of presence and immersion contributes to a more engaging and impactful interaction with products.

This positive response to the realism of the VR product showcase experience emphasizes the potential of VR technology to bridge the gap between physical and digital interactions. It also points to the continuous advancements in VR technology that enable users to engage with products in ways that closely resemble real-life experiences. As VR technology continues to progress, the level of realism and immersion is likely to improve further, offering even more compelling and convincing product showcases.

Fig. 13. Would you recommend VR for product showcase
Around 88.2 percent would like to recommend the VR product showcase based on their experience which emphasizes the potential of VR technology to bridge the gap between physical and digital interactions.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The VR revolution is only beginning to unveil its transformative potential. As technology continues to evolve and consumer expectations rise, companies that embrace VR are poised to reshape the landscape of consumer engagement, sales strategies, and product offerings. By providing unparalleled immersive experiences and data-driven insights, VR is set to propel businesses into a new era of enhanced performance and innovation.

A product showcase based on virtual reality can provide an immersive and engaging experience for users, allowing them to interact with a product in the virtual environment. The usage of virtual reality technology can enhance the traditional product showcase by providing a more interactive and personalized experience, allowing users to see and experience a product in a way that was not previously possible. Incorporating virtual reality technology in a product showcase can create an immersive and captivating encounter for users, enabling them to engage with the product within a virtual setting. This approach offers a personalized and interactive experience that surpasses the conventional product showcase. To create a successful product showcase based on virtual reality, it is important to consider both the functional and non-functional requirements, as well as the hardware and software requirements. This includes ensuring that the virtual environment and product showcase are optimized for a smooth and responsive experience and that the hardware and software components are compatible with the chosen VR platform.

REFERENCES

- [1] Jiang, Y. (2022). Based on Virtual Reality Technology Research on Innovation and Design of Ceramic Painting Products. *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, 2022.
- [2] Saputra, A. P., Budiarta, K., & Rinas, W. (2016). Design and Analysis of Online Shop Display Based on Augmented Reality Technology. *Int. J. Eng. Emerg. Technol.*, 1(1), 61-64.
- [3] Verma, R., Dhanta, N., & Shukla, U. (2023). Augmented Reality Product Showcase E-commerce Application. Available at SSRN 4361319.
- [4] Luo, H. (2022). Product 3D virtual display scene modelling based on augmented reality technology. *International Journal of Product Development*, 26(1-4), 131-142.
- [5] Jun-Zhu, Z. and Yu-Gao, Z., 2022, July. Display Design Based on Virtual Reality Technology VR-Platform Platform. In *2022 7th IEEE International Conference on Data Science in Cyberspace (DSC)* (pp. 556-563). IEEE.
- [6] Kong, X., Liu, D. and Min, L., 2020. VR technology in marketing from the perspective of customer experience. *IEEE Access*, 8, pp.162581-162587.
- [7] Y. Chi and Q. An, "Design and Implementation of Virtual Campus System based on VR Technology," 2022 2nd Asia Conference on Information Engineering (ACIE), Haikou, China, 2022, pp. 44-47, doi: 10.1109/ACIE55485.2022.00015.
- [8] Henriques, A.C. and Winkler, I., 2020, November. Automotive Marketing Research and Virtual Reality: A Systematic Literature Review. In *2020 22nd Symposium on Virtual and Augmented Reality (SVR)* (pp. 339-345).
- [9] X. -Y. Huang, M. -S. Tsai and C. -C. Huang, "3D Virtual-Reality Interaction System," 2019 IEEE International Conference on Consumer Electronics - Taiwan (ICCE-TW), Yilan, Taiwan, 2019, pp. 1-2.
- [10] Y. Kuang and X. Bai, "The Research of Virtual Reality Scene Modeling Based on Unity 3D," 2018 13th International Conference on Computer Science & Education (ICCSE), Colombo, Sri Lanka, 2018, pp. 1-3.
- [11] N. Singh and S. Singh, "Virtual reality: A brief survey," 2017 International Conference on Information Communication and Embedded Systems (ICICES), Chennai, India, 2017, pp. 1- 6.
- [12] Ekpo, A.E., Riley, B.K., Thomas, K.D., Yvaire, Z., Gerri, G.R.H. and Muñoz, I.I., 2015. As worlds collide: The role of marketing management in customer-to-customer interactions. *Journal of Business Research*, 68(1), pp.119-126.
- [13] Lv, H., Zhang, J., & Long, H. (2019, September). Research on the development of virtual pavilion based on virtual reality. In *2019 International Conference on Virtual Reality and Intelligent Systems (ICVRIS)* (pp. 62-64). IEEE.

- [14] Zhang, J. (2020, April). Application research of display design based on virtual reality. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 1533, No. 3, p. 032003). IOP Publishing.
- [15] Wijaya, P. K., & Hermawan, A. (2018). E-Marketing Applications Based On Virtual Reality Using Sostac Planning Method On Sales Property. *Tech-E*, 1(2), 16-25.
- [16] Lai, H., & Lu, M. (2021). Dynamic VR Display System of Digital Garment Display Design Based on 5G Virtual Reality Technology. In *Big Data Analytics for Cyber-Physical System in Smart City: BDCPS 2020, 28-29 December 2020, Shanghai, China* (pp. 1191-1198). Springer Singapore.
- [17] Sun, D., Xu, L., Zhang, L., & Cui, N. (2019, August). How Augmented Reality Affects People's Perceptions: Adoption of AR in Product Display Improves Consumers' Product Attitude. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 1288, No. 1, p. 012037). IOP Publishing.
- [18] Jiang, Y. (2022). Based on Virtual Reality Technology Research on Innovation and Design of Ceramic Painting Products. *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, 2022.
- [19] Zhang, Z., & Zhang, L. (2022). Dynamic display design of cultural and creative products based on digital augmented reality technology. *Mobile Information Systems*, 2022, 1-13.
- [20] Yan, X., Liu, F., & Mojtahed, K. (2022). Application of Virtual Reality Technology in Visual Optimization of Product Appearance Design. *Security and Communication Networks*, 2022.
- [21] Tian, W. (2013). The analysis of product design research based on virtual reality technology. *Applied Mechanics and Materials*, 347, 3123-3127.